

Heat transfer mechanisms of a novel inductive power transformer and coupled simulation using FEA

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Calculation of the temperature fields developed in Solid State Transformers (SST) is a critical step of their design process in order to ensure their stable and efficient operation. This paper studies the heat transfer mechanisms of a novel Inductive Power Transformer (IPT) submerged into a biodegradable dielectric fluid, in the context of the SSTAR Horizon project. A one-way coupled electromagnetic-thermal simulation model is presented using the commercial software ANSYS. The proposed model is later used to calculate the temperature of the IPT structural parts based on the electromagnetic losses. The results highlight the increased temperature levels and the subsequent need to include a cooling system in the layout.

Keywords: Solid State Transformer, Inductive Power Transformer, Heat Transfer Mechanisms, Finite Element Analysis

INTRODUCTION

The architecture of electrical networks has changed from passive to active and controllable with high renewable energy and storage penetration. As a result, their infrastructures need to be upgraded, including advanced, power converters and transformers. In distribution networks, the most promising solution for the replacement of the conventional transformer seems to be the Solid State Transformer (SST) [1], the design of which is an open a field of research that has attracted many experts trying to optimize technical aspects such as electromagnetic and thermal properties and heat transfer mechanisms in a sustainable and cost-efficient way. Additionally, more recent research focuses on Inductive Power Transformers (IPT), a type of SST that has a wider application field as the primary and secondary windings are not connected. For example, in [2] the performance of an IPT for wireless charging is studied through a novel simulation model that combines an electrical circuit with a nonlinear finite element model. Also, the authors of [3] compared the performance of a 50 kW IPT for two operation frequencies (22 and 85 kHz), evaluating the consequent losses analytically, through finite element and circuit analysis.

This paper aims to investigate the heat transfer mechanisms of a novel 50 kW IPT designed to operate at 1.5 kV / 0.4 kV, 50 kHz, submerged into a biodegradable dielectric fluid, in the context of Horizon SSTAR project. A one-way coupled electromagnetic-thermal model is developed using ANSYS, which calculates the temperature of the IPT parts based on the electromagnetic losses.

METHODOLOGY

The simplified geometry and the heat flow pathways are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: IPT inside tank and the heat flow pathways.

During operation, the IPT generates heat due to the electromagnetic field between its primary and secondary windings, resulting in power loss. The uneven heat generation between primary and secondary parts results in the formation of localized hot spots. The total thermal energy produced is transferred by convection through the dielectric fluid and then dispersed into the environment mainly by convection through the walls of the tank. Also, the primary and secondary shield walls and tank walls absorb and emit thermal energy in the form of electromagnetic waves. This thermal radiation contributes to the heat transfer process.

The modelling approach is based on the interaction and transfer of data between the electromagnetic and the thermal model. The

coupling scheme is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: The proposed coupling scheme.

The system of the equations is solved using ANSYS Maxwell-Icepak software in order to calculate the magnetic and thermal characteristics. The computational mesh consists of tetrahedral elements and it is in the order of $1e6$ cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The temperatures developed in the SST and the dielectric losses are presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Fig. 3: Temperature of the SST.

Fig. 4: Dielectric losses of the SST.

According to the results, the SST may develop temperatures up to 210 °C, especially in the area close to the primary winding. Moreover, the

dielectric losses occur mostly between the primary and secondary winding, as expected, with maximum value lower than $9 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ W/m}^3$. Taking these results into account, the authors consider that a simple yet effective improvement in the design of the SST would be the implementation of a forced liquid cooling system, utilizing the biodegradable dielectric fluid in the tank. This shall be a future step in the context of the SSTAR Horizon project, where the SST module shall be developed (including forced liquid cooling system) and the simulations shall be validated through experimental results.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper assesses the heat transfer mechanisms of a novel SST which is currently under development in the context of the SSTAR project. A one-way coupled electromagnetic-thermal model is developed using ANSYS, to calculate temperature of the transformer's structural parts based on the electromagnetic losses. According to the results, the temperature may reach up to 210 °C. This could be sufficiently moderated by including a cooling system in the layout, which is the next step of this research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported financially by the Horizon research project SSTAR, GA: 101069702, which is gratefully acknowledged by the authors.

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